

PHYSICAL FITNESS OF NATIONAL WRESTLING ATHLETES

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Abstract: The merits of our country's wrestlers in carrying the flag of Uzbekistan high in international competitions at the world sports arenas are incomparable. The issue of physical fitness of national wrestling athletes was studied and analyzed in the article.

Key words: sports, national wrestling, development, training, wrestling methods, physical training, kinematics and dynamics.

INTRODUCTION

Popularization of physical education and sports in new Uzbekistan, promotion of a healthy lifestyle among the population, implementation of specific programs that help to strengthen the health of the population in the field of physical education and sports, wide involvement of young people in sports and consistent measures are being taken to select talented athletes from among them, to form national teams with skilled athletes who provide high results in sports, and to ensure proper participation of the country in international sports arenas. The Uzbek people should be proud of their national sports. As a result of the care of the leadership of our country in the development of physical education and sports, our national sports are developing and becoming more popular. Uzbek national wrestling methods have a long history, and today these wrestling methods are widespread in all Asian countries and among a number of European nations. Eastern thinkers have written about wrestling methods, their formation, types and skilled wrestlers in their works.

National wrestling is one of the means of raising a physically fit and spiritually mature person. Currently, national wrestling types are developing widely in our country. Athletes of our republic have been successfully participating in Asian, European and world championships.

The Bukhara style of wrestling, which is considered the national wrestling of Uzbekistan, became "Kurash" as a result of the scientific, methodological and practical researches of advanced experts. With this, the fight became more attractive and enjoyable.

Currently, secondary schools, vocational colleges, and higher education system teach national wrestling methods in the process of physical education. The pedagogical process of training professional athletes in wrestling circles of sports schools is being improved in accordance with the requirements of the time. The process of training professional wrestlers is a multi-stage and pedagogical process that requires regular physical, technical-tactical, theoretical and spiritual preparation of wrestlers, as well as hard work.

Thanks to independence, the Uzbek struggle has spread to all continents of the globe, the resounding of the Uzbek language of struggle, halal, stop and other words of all nations and peoples has recognized the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Uzbek people, by the whole world community. is a clear example of the fact that it is obtained. Based on the importance of Uzbek wrestling in the education of young people, it is appropriate to carry out the following activities in order to educate our young people as well-rounded, healthy, spiritually mature people.

DISCUSSION

Physical training of a wrestler is one of the important components of sports training and is a process aimed at developing physical qualities - strength, endurance, flexibility, agility and quickness.

The main tasks of physical training are:

Improving the level of health of athletes and the functional capabilities of

various systems of their body.

Development of physical qualities in a unit that meets the unique characteristics of sports wrestling.

Physical training is divided into general, auxiliary and special training.

The general physical fitness of a wrestler is the foundation, necessary basis for achieving high results. It mainly provides the solution of the following tasks:

All-round harmonious development of the wrestler's body, increase of its functional capabilities, development of physical qualities.

Increase the level of health.

Proper use of active rest during intense training and competition.

General physical training includes the collection of various tools. Among them, exercises performed in shells and with shells, exercises performed with a partner on a special trainer, general developmental exercises taken from other types of sports: acrobatics, athletics, sports games, suzi, etc. are distinguished. Auxiliary physical training is designed to create a special basis necessary for effective performance of a large volume of work aimed at the development of special movement skills. It has a rather narrow and specific direction and solves the following tasks:

Developing qualities that are more specific to fighting.

Selective development of muscle groups that are largely involved in the wrestler's movements. As advanced means of auxiliary physical training, such exercises are used, which, according to their kinematic and dynamic structure and neuromuscular tension, are suitable for the main actions performed by the wrestler during the competition. Among such exercises, the following can be distinguished: execution of various methods of struggle by pointing; exercises performed on special training devices; exercises with wrestlers' mannequins.

The special physical training of a wrestler is aimed at developing the

qualities of movement in strict accordance with the requirements imposed by the characteristics of the wrestlers' competition.

The special physical training of wrestlers is mainly carried out on the wrestling mat and is aimed at developing the most important movement qualities in movement skills. That's why competitive exercises involving various possible complications are used as the main means of special physical training.

Such complex exercises increase the impact on the body of the wrestler. For example, throwing a partner in a heavier weight category, training competitions are performed by changing partners, etc. All these exercises provide an opportunity to develop one or another mechanism of energy supply, have a complex effect on the training of the wrestler and at the same time increase his physical and technical-tactical preparation.

All the indicated types of physical training are inextricably linked. Inadequate evaluation of any types of physical training during the training will ultimately prevent the improvement of sports skills. Therefore, it is very important to observe the optimal ratio of the types of physical training indicated during training. Its numerical expression is not considered a constant size, but changes depending on the wrestlers' qualifications, their special characteristics, the period of the training process, and the current state of the body.

Strength and the methodology of its development. "Strength", which is a physical quality, means the ability of a wrestler to overcome the opponent's resistance or resist him due to muscle tension.

The following types of strength are distinguished: general and special, absolute and relative, quick and explosive, strength endurance.

General strength is the strength displayed by an athlete without reference to specific movements of the wrestler. Special strength is shown by the athlete in special movements corresponding to the competition movements. Absolute strength is characterized by the power capabilities of the athlete, which are

manifested in the movements of a very large nature. In wrestling, it is important for getting one-on-ones with power.

Relative strength, that is, the strength corresponding to 1 kg of the athlete's weight, is an indicator of the wrestler's ability to overcome his personal weight. It is important to perform these methods quickly.

Quick strength is reflected in the ability of muscles to quickly perform movements associated with overcoming relatively small external resistance.

Explosive power describes the ability to manifest large stresses in a short time according to its intensity.

Endurance is the athlete's ability to exert muscle tension for a relatively long time. The following techniques are used to develop the wrestler's strength: repeated tension; short-term maximum voltages; growing more and more

weights, percussion, joint effect; variability; isometric tension techniques.

The method of repeated stresses is that the athlete repeats the exercise with weights equal to 70-80% of the maximum weight while performing the exercise "to the last breath". This method involves performing a series of strength exercises. Each series - "until the last breath", 3-4 series in total, the rest interval between series is 3-4 min.

One type of repeated stress method is the dynamic stress method. It is characterized by performing exercises at a limit speed of 20-30% of the maximum weight. In this case, large muscle tension is achieved not due to heavy weight, but due to high-speed movement.

The short-term maximum tension method is currently the most effective for increasing absolute muscle strength. It involves working with weights at the limit and close to the limit. In muscle training, the style of maximum tension is manifested in simulators and in one approach using one or two movements, in exercises performed with a heavy barbell (silent, swinging, lifting a hand, sitting and standing). A total of 3-4 approaches are performed during the training. Rest

interval between approaches - 3-5 min. The progressive weight method involves gradually increasing the amount of resistance during one training session as well as the next.

It is recommended to start with a weight equal to 50% of the weight that the athlete can lift 10 times (10 MT) in the first approach. In the second approach, the exercise is performed with a weight of 75% from 10 MT, and in the third approach - with a weight of 100% from 10 MT. A total of 3 approaches are performed during the training. Rest interval between approaches is 2-4 min. In each approach, the exercise is performed at the limit speed until clearly exhausted.

The percussive method is based on the percussive stimulation of muscle groups by using the kinematic energy of the falling weight and the weight of the individual body. Absorption of the energy of the decreasing weight by the exercising muscles helps the muscles to move to an active state, the rapid development of working tension, and creates the possibility of additional tension in the muscle. This ensures the speed and speed of the next pushing action and the rapid transition from the backlog to the work to be overcome.

As a method of using a percussive method of developing the explosive power of the legs, we can say high jump exercises performed with high or long jumps. The exercise is performed by falling to the ground from a height of 70-80 cm with the knees slightly bent, and jumping up quickly and violently. Jumps in series: in 2-3 series, 8-10 jumps are performed in each series. Rest interval between series is 3-5 min. Exercise is done twice a week.

The joint effect method depends on the fact that the development of the strength capabilities of the wrestler occurs directly during the performance of specialized exercises. At the same time, the wrestler's strength skills and technical-tactical movements are developed and improved. As an example of the use of the joint effect method in wrestling, such exercises can be given, in which a wrestler improves his technical movements with an opponent of a heavier weight

class.

It is very important to determine the optimal size of the weight. An excessively large size leads to a violation of the composition of movement skills, which in turn has a negative effect on movement technique. Variation method mainly involves performing special exercises with weights of different weights. Exercises are performed serially with partners of different weights. In one series, first 10-12 throws are performed with an opponent of a heavier weight category, then 15-16 throws are performed with an opponent of the same weight category, after which 10-12 throws are performed with an opponent of the same weight category. A total of 3 series will be performed. Rest interval - 3-4 min. The variant method is especially effective in developing quick-strength qualities (moderate, small).

Endurance and the method of its development. Endurance of a wrestler is the ability to perform actions at a high speed during the entire competition and to conduct several competitions with intensity during the entire competition. A high level of endurance allows a wrestler to master large training and competition tasks, to fully realize his movement skills in competitive activities.

CONCLUSION

When doing such exercises, a number of methodological conditions must be met:

- 1) warm-up exercises must be included before starting exercises;
- 2) setting specific goals, for example, touching a certain point of the body or object;
- 3) performing stretching exercises serially in a certain sequence: for hands, for body, for legs;
- 4) perform relaxation exercises between series of stretching exercises;
- 5) gradually increasing their amplitude while performing exercises;
- 6) when performing exercises, it should be taken into account that the most

basic method of developing mobility is the method of repetition.

Flexibility can be greatly increased during a training session consisting of moderate stretching exercises of 25-50 repetitions, depending on the individual abilities of the participants, twice daily for a month or two.

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